

Open Science in Italian Universities. Advantage or unnecessary policies?

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Abstract

This paper focuses on the policies of Italian Universities on Open Science and Open Access. Open Science is a movement that wants to make all academic research more accessible. The academic endeavor is clearly demonstrated in the declarations of Bethesda, Berlin, and Messina, as well as in the active backing for OS policies. Italian universities, especially in the last decade, launched under the supervision of CRUI guidelines and strategic framework of actions.

In this work, we started exploring the field. We observed the definition of Open Science and Access, the main declarations and the policies and guidelines launched in the Italian academia. As a second step, we used the staggered difference-in-difference to evaluate the possible impact of such policies. Due to the lack of data at disposal, we scraped the SCOPUS database for the publications in the sociology field from Italian universities. The analysis, a preliminary approach that could see improvements in the future, seems to support our hypothesis about the positive impact of the policies in the recent years.

Introduction

For scholars, the possibility to publish their own works and to divulge it to the wider public has become of the utmost importance (Patrick O'Neil & Sachis, 1994). For them, it is possible to achieve this not only via their own universities and research centres, but also through massive research infrastructures and agencies interested in spreading their reports, documents, analysis to have the chance to obtain funding as much as scientific renown (Fabre, Egret, Schöpfel, & Azeroual, 2021).

Despite it not being a novelty, the general notion of Open Science has become relevant to the public discourse concerning the academic and research worlds

(Schouppe & Burgelman, 2018). Under the umbrella of Open Science, we can find a different, wide array of elements. Open Science comprehends, in its taxonomy, concepts such as Open Data, Open Science Evaluation and so on. This taxonomy will be further addressed later on (FOSTER, 2023).

For now, what is relevant is to be clear that under the concept of Open Science we find a vast array of tools and concepts which shape the reality of science itself (Morzy, 2015). This vast array of elements is under scrutiny and analysis, together with its promises of an enhanced arena for researchers and experts in which to move and divulge their own works and ideas (Ogungbeni & Al., 2018).

The recent trend in Open Science is deeply connected with a revolution, in the broadest sense of the term, on how to perform science (Spellman, Gilbert, & Corker, 2017). This revolution is in turn linked to new technologies that increase the possibility for a paper to be divulged effectively. At the same time, this revolution does not concern solely the product of research – i.e., datasets, papers, journals – but the entire procedures involved in performing research (Vinkler, 2010).

Open Science has entered massively inside universities, including Italian ones. The first massive step in Europe was set by the Berlin Declaration of 2003 (Max Planck Institute, 2003), with Italian universities signing the declaration in 2004, the first one being the University of Messina (Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, 2004). This first step was in the direction of more open science and access in the academic space of the Bel Paese. CRUI (*Conferenza dei Rettori delle Università Italiane*) dedicated an entire working group on the diffusion of Open Science in Italy, creating documents and guidelines to support those universities moving in this direction.

In this work, starting from the diffusion of Open Science in the Italian research environment, we will try first to present an overview of the existing literature and policies that in Italy describe and support Open Science inside the academic world. We will try to show which universities began to invest in, and actively move themselves towards, the adoption of Open Science and, finally, we will try to determine how it is possible to evaluate their commitment and the effectiveness of such investments – not only from an economic perspective, but mainly from the standpoint of cultural and political effects.

What this paper hopes to accomplish is to highlight the attempts made and the policies enacted, while trying to underline the visible results. Open Science

can be a game-changer for Italian academia, opening the way for a wide-range of new actions and collaborations between institutions and scholars. At the same time, it is shown to be a good pragmatic choice, considering the investments of money and resources committed by entities such as the European Union and its organizations and institutions.

Open Science and its principles

Open Science is a concept which is becoming widely diffused in the current environment of research (Cfr. Pontika & Al., 2015; Vicente-Saez & Martinez-Fuentes, 2018; National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2018). Actually, it may be possible to consider the idea of science as an “open environment” as an integral, original component of science’s own concept (Cornillon, Gallagher, & Sgouros, 2003). Science bases its own diffusion on the possibility for other scholars to get to know something from someone and, as “dwarf on the shoulder of the giants”, to produce something new out of this process of knowledge accumulation. Along the years, science has become more involved with the interests of public and private companies and agencies (Mazzucato, 2018). The need for increased funding in order to perform better and to deliver more advanced research had its impact, and the capitalistic tendencies created a sort of loop in which research became more and more a private affair and, to necessity, something to be protected with patents and copyrights laws.

We can observe this tendency in the editorial reality of scientific papers and journals. Companies as SAGE, Emerald, Elsevier, are examples of companies which control a necessary flux of information for scholars and experts: the publication. The need for scholars to increase their own “score” in order to access better positions inside academia, made the control of the most important source of such score, that is publications, the field for an economic battle. This gives a glimpse into the current environment of modern academia, the same one in which Open Science is spreading. (Delfanti, 2010)

The first step of the analysis will be defining what we mean as Open Science. UNESCO defined it as the following:

“Open science is defined as an inclusive construct that combines various movements and practices aiming to make multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone, to increase scientific

collaborations and sharing of information for the benefits of science and society, and to open the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication to societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community. It comprises all scientific disciplines and aspects of scholarly practices, including basic and applied sciences, natural and social sciences and the humanities, and it builds on the following key pillars: open scientific knowledge, open science infrastructures, science communication, open engagement of societal actors and open dialogue with other knowledge systems." (UNESCO, 2023)

As per this definition, Open Science is a broad term which encompasses a number of items and tools. Inside this term many different aspects of the research activity fall, if not all of them. Concerning this, the FOSTER project, sponsored by the European Union, can better illustrate what the Open Science term can include. FOSTER is an online portal and project that provide toolkits and information for both activists and scientists. Moreover, the FOSTER portal provides different taxonomies which describe graphically aspects of making science as part of an Open Science environment (FOSTER, 2023).

Figure 1: Taxonomy of Open Science

Source: Foster project

Figure 1 shows in detail the taxonomy of the term Open Science. Its broad sense allows us to address a variety of aspects, going from access to projects

to their evaluation. Open Science is not made only by articles and papers freely available on the web. It also means the complete transparency of the research process, as much as encompassing all the necessary policies governmental and non-governmental bodies must perform in order to shift the scientific environment towards broader accessibility and transparency (Gomez-Dias & Recio, 2021).

Open Science comprehends a variety of aspects that must be considered. The history of the movement itself (Gomez-Dias & Recio, 2021) is long and variegated and we just, partially, dwell later on it. We can say, in a very summarizing way, Open Science comprehends an ample segment of sciences as a whole. It concerns the legal aspects, as much as the framework of policies built around science as a policy affair (Gomez-Dias & Recio, 2021).

One element of Open Science is of particular interest on the side of the dissemination, and so on the side of universities and scholars: Open Access. Open Access is usually recognized as the possibility to access different tools, especially journals and papers, freely (Bailey, Jr., 2006). We can define Open Access with the words of the already mentioned Berlin Declaration of 2003, a first example of interpretation of the term itself. The declaration is recognized as a landmark in the process of acceptance of Open Access as a viable methodology and way of doing research. It was also a fundamental step for European academics and academies to enter into contact with the previous *Declaration of the Budapest Open Access Initiative*, the *ECHO Charter* and the *Bethesda Statement on Open Access Publishing*. The Berlin Declaration, built on input by the Max Planck Institute, stated two important elements relevant to this work: the definition of what is Open Access for academia, and the prediction of a transition towards a digital environment for the same academia (Max Planck Institute, 2003).

In there, Open Access is defined as something that is to be taken into consideration in regard of many aspects of research. Earlier Open Science has been labelled as a broad umbrella. That is true also for Open Access (OA). OA considers data, raw materials, research, and the final outcomes of their combination in the form of papers and monographs. It is only natural the Berlin Declaration states clearly how these products should be considered under such 'broad umbrella' (Max Planck Institute, 2003).

The declaration states that everything – from a dataset to a tool – must be free to use, diffuse, copy, under a clear and transparent electronic permission form. This is all part of a process for the expansion of Open Access. Both the

transmission phase – the moment in which information is moved between two sources – and the means of transmission – i.e. the accessibility of the platform itself – are relevant for those who campaign for Open Access. The web is thus a fundamental part of this effort.

These principles form the core of the FAIR principles for data. FAIR is the acronym for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. FAIR is the result of the 2016 project '*FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship*' (GoFAIR, 2023). Its scope was the creation of a standard for data usage in line with those tendencies and new movements emerging inside academia which have been highlighted above. FAIR, together with the project GoFAIR, established an opportunity for stakeholders to implement the concept inside their own institutions. It is a way to disseminate the practice itself more than specific tools – that can be seen as the documents and the guidelines prepared by the team. The concept behind FAIR is strictly connected with the digitalization of the scientific environment, and thus it is also linked with the second part of the Berlin Declaration (Castro & Al., 2022).

How the digitalization of tools had the chance to modify how we do, perceive, and perform, our scientific efforts and works has been briefly anticipated above. Open Access finds a very fertile ground for progress in the offer of digital tools, in the accessibility they offer their users, and in the possibility to prosper outside the traditional tools of publication and diffusion (Cfr. Bezuidenhout, 2022; Coşuleanu, Grecu, & Bahnaru, 2022)

It stands clear that private companies and actors still exercise domination over the digital world of academic publishing. Sites as Scopus, Web of Science, PubMed and many other belong to private actors – as Elsevier – that usually are also the same ones which control consistent shares of the editorial reality. Digital tools offer the possibility to other interested parties to enter into the contest for publications, their diffusion, and the management of data. One of the points highlighted by the Berlin Declaration is to pave the way for a new approach to the use of those tools by the stakeholders that populate this reality.

Research Infrastructures and Open Sciences

FAIR, as FOSTER, represents a newfound interest from stakeholders and actors as the European Union on dwelling more and better on the topic of Open Science (Mačiulienė, 2022). An interest that not only was framed in a specific set of legislative actions (Gomez-Dias & Recio, 2021), but at the same

time saw more investment on the side of projects, and infrastructures, capable to support the diffusion of such movement between scholars and their institutions.

FOSTER represents one of such elements. We cited it before, as source of our taxonomy of Open Science. Plus (*Fostering the practical implementation of Open Science in Horizon 2020 and beyond*) is an EU-funded project which comprise 11 partners in 6 nations (FOSTER, 2023). While programs devoted to the diffusion of the concept of Open Science or Open Access around the world or the academic community already exist, FOSTER – as the title suggest – fosters the capacities of the partners and interested stakeholders in using Open Science in their everyday activities. The taxonomy briefly illustrated above is one of such tools, already shown on several universities' websites. It is one of the many different tools provided by FOSTER. Some of the other tools are publications specialized in explaining how to use and interact with Open Science, how to publish and produce better results with it, how to integrate Open Science in one's own community of interest – academic, cultural or civic one. FOSTER also produces tools for data and text analysis and mining to expand and better understand the sense of Open Science to diffuse openly new tools themselves.

OPERAS, on the other hand, constitutes another kind of approach to Open Science and, differently from the previous examples, it does not take the form of an initiative, instead taking that of a proper research infrastructure (OPERAS, 2023). Recently added to the ESFRI (European Strategic Forum on Research Infrastructure) of the European Union, OPERAS includes project as TRIPLE, VERA, PALOMERA. Each one of them has, as kernel, the possibility to expand the set of Open Access and Open Science tools available to the citizen, the expert, and the stakeholder. In the case of TRIPLE, for example – which we will use to observe the numbers of publications from the Italian universities – we have the kind of research engine as in Google Scholar or the well-known SCOPUS (Elsevier, 2023). In the case of TRIPLE, the contents and the search engine are in line with the FAIR principles of transparency and access. PALOMERA, instead, is not a tool but an approach to the policies that European countries adopt on Open Access monographs, with the declared goal to lay comprehensive support for the political stakeholder interested in approaching such a topic.

RIs ad project – as FAIR and FOSTER - represents a great opportunity for the interested part in the diffusion of Open Science in the academic reality.

Despite being a novelty in the field, the rising interests in the openness of everything connected with making science, seems to make worthy of investments and time the creation of such complex tools and projects, to support the actors involved in this process.

The Italian Universities and Open Science

The Messina Declaration is a sort of follow-up to the Berlin one and it had the scope of unifying the efforts of Italian universities towards Open Science and its diffusion. Signed in November 2004, it took more the form of an intent declaration than of a real policy document (Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, 2004). Despite that, it is possible to consider it as a sort of first approach, a programmatic one, in which Italian universities and their association – the CRUI – began to reason on the possible ways to enact the concept of Open Science inside their own confines. 75 universities in Italy adhered to the declaration. Other than signing it, the efforts of CRUI were directed to the creation of more practical tools to enact what, otherwise, would have remained a sort of a dead track for Open Science. The Observatory on Open Science of CRUI takes care of creating guidelines and policy documents each single university can adopt in its own context. The adherence to the Declarations is not, by itself, a commitment to enact more policies in Open Science, neither it is the participation in the Observatory's activities.

The independence Italian universities enjoy grants them the chance to move in autonomy in the field of Open Science. CRUI offers a sort of backbone on which the institutions can find some space for actions and resources useful to start their own initiatives. The documents CRUI prepared are practical guidelines and policy proposals each department or faculty, or even the entire university, can adopt for its own university press, libraries, and in general to regulate the access to documents and data.

Another element spread by CRUI was CRUI-CARE, Coordination for Access to Electronic Resources (*Coordinamento per l'Accesso alle Risorse Elettroniche*). In this case, CARE was an attempt – in which many universities converged – to generate a common framework of reference for the access, usage, diffusion of digital contents. Moreover, it was relevant its mediation role between editors and universities for different kind of contracts regarding such digital resources. The transformative contracts are part of the 1-to-1 exchange between universities, their own libraries and presses, departments, and the editor themselves. We briefly described the role performed by CARE

since we will see below how many entities in the Italian academic framework decided to ground their own adherence to Open access on the transformative agreements, instead of developing their own policies.

The policies adopted by Italian universities are the focus of this work. We are interested in observing how several universities – both private and public -, all signature parties to the Messina Declaration, adapted its principles to their frameworks of action. We focus our attention only on the Declaration's signatories, among which we find a majority of Italian universities. It has been decided to focus specifically on them to better see whether they opted for a concrete application, or instead for the mere observance, of the Open Science principles. Adherence and effectiveness are of course different sides of a policy implementation. In the case of Italian universities, adherence to the principles of Open Science that CRUI supported assumed different forms.

The signing of the Messina Declaration – and, consequently, of the Berlin one, together with its principles – meant for many universities the creation of ad hoc policies to improve the Open Science actions inside their own borders. Many – 51 of our totals – created specific guidelines and policies. These policies can vary from strategic guidelines underlining a general intent to more precise and concrete policies.

In turn, these policies could describe the meaning of Open Science, how to implement it actively, the tools that it is possible to use in order to achieve its goals. If we take as an example the policy established by the University of Rome “La Sapienza”, it is possible to see elements that are considered relevant. On one hand, we have the adherence to principles stated in laws and declarations – i.e., the Law 112/2013 on Open science, together with the Berlin and Messina declarations cited before. On the other hand, the policy states the creation of a specific commission inside the university, the steps the University Press has to implement toward open access and, a point often mentioned in the literature, the open access of doctoral dissertations after their delivery and defence.

The policies enacted by “La Sapienza” do not exist in a vacuum, as other universities which endorsed the principles of Open Science often decided to keep similar positions. Other universities which, instead, have no policy on such topics tend to find their own way to the Open Science field thanks to CRUI-CARE – concerning the relation with their own presses and the journals – or to deliberately push their own libraries in supporting Open Access, implementing new possible ways of publishing those books and journals

written inside the university and signing – as in CRUI-CARE – ad hoc contracts with other journals.

It is possible to observe how the policies enacted by Italian universities shape an environment where Open Science has better prospects to prosper. Despite this, the obligations for the researcher and the institution are few, but relevant. One concerns, and this is the case of “La Sapienza” itself, the storage of papers and other works inside the IRIS repository, with the possibility of receiving contractual support with eventual editors for the eventual copyright issues. It is important to note that, with a precise policy such as that adopted the Roman university, it becomes possible for authors – i.e., professors, researchers, doctoral students – to receive the necessary support in navigating the complexity of the bureaucracy behind the publication of a single paper. The efforts spent on Open Science can be advantageous for universities, if we look at them as giving further chances to scholars to expand their network, as much as getting renown thanks to the spread of papers and datasets – integral parts of the concept of Open Science itself.

The RIs in the Italian landscape

We briefly introduced the topic of RIs in the panorama of ESFRI and European research at large. Italian universities, but also private stakeholder and other research performing or funding organization (RPOs and RFOs) joined the efforts of ESFRI in promoting new infrastructures. We cited both OPERAS and DARIAH before, which can count on a strong Italian node. OPERAS, in particular, see between its partner Net7 and Lexis. Net7 is a private companies devoted to developing new tools for academic research and it’s the main tech partner of the infrastructure as a whole. Lexis, on the other hand, represents the private sector of editorial publishing in the academic reality of the country (OPERAS, 2023).

Their presence in OPERAS suggests a more and more present connection between private and public actors in a general effort to re-shape the nature of academic reality in the country. This mixture of public-private partners is representative of a broader effort as exemplified by the CRUI policies described above.

The existence of RIs in the Italian academic landscape is strongly linked with the Council of National Research (CNR) of Italy, the main RFO-RPO operating in synergy with the Ministry of Research and University and the

other governmental components in the country. CNR is the main partners of DARIAH, OPERAS, but also of CESSDA, the ESS or RISIS, and many other infrastructures that are creating a variegated environment in the Italian landscape of SSH.

If the cited projects came from European and trans-national experience, there are also attempts to move on the national scale, as in the case of FOSSR. We will not dwell in the nature and the processes of such infrastructures, but it is necessary to specify that mostly these projects move toward two directions: the creation of new policies or processes capable to impact the policy makers; the generation of new tools useful for the researchers -i.e., massive dataset data-rich, search engine for Open Access, analysis tools (Fabrizio & Al., 2024) It is the case of OPERAS and the development of the Triple tool (Breitfuss & Al., 2020), or the datasets located in CESSDA and RISIS. Moreover, we can observe policy attempts trying to change the editorial perspective on Open Access books in PALOMERA.

On the first hand, this variety makes difficult for any research to comprehensively approach the field and to observe the sum of such interactions and interventions. On the other hand, the possibility to spot and observe the single interventions offer a peculiar point of view for the researcher and the possibility to observe, first-hand, almost on the field, the possible impact and to evaluate their usefulness.

In this paper, we could not concentrate on the precise analysis of infrastructures on the academic landscape, prioritizing the effects of new policies in Italian universities and their capacity to influence the open access publications in a very narrow SSH field. Nevertheless, the presence of new infrastructures exerts an influence on the research field and on the researchers themselves (Florio, 2019). There are different possibilities for evaluating the RIs and their impacts (Iannace, 2023; Hallonsten, 2020; Florio, 2019) but it is a field rich of possible experimentation which deserve a proper investigation.

Due to how the RIs are diffusing and the role of Open Science as a pivotal factor in the evolution of SSH, it is without doubt the two realities will be strictly connected in the near future. The European Union foster Open Science in all its investment in the RIs (ESFRI, 2020), and this will shape also the national landscape. The presence of policies and their impacts – as we will see in the next paragraph – is a symbol the role of Open Science is being included

in the efforts, at least officially, of the Italian RPOs. If this efforts is beyond the pure formality, is something deserving a proper investigation.

The impact of Open Science Policies on Italian universities

We presented the case of how Italian RPOs, in particular universities, launched policies devoted to Open Science in their own organizations. We also briefly faced their relation with RIs in the framework of SSH. In this section, we will try to underline if the cited policies could, or not, have a real impact in the scientific production of Italian universities.

Our main hypothesis concerning their application is connected both with the conceptualization of qualitative and quantitative aspects of research, in this case with a more focused approach on the former.

The quantity of research, as already partly established above, is connected with different tendencies inside the academia. The need for both the institutions and the scholars to focus on academic production on increased scale to keep their rankings high and thus to access more resources produces the notorious effect labelled as the “publish or perish” mindset, which exercised quite an impact upon the size of available publications.

Quality keeps its connection with the diffusion of Open Science inside academia. It is also relatively harder to estimate in the case of scientific works. Is it quality an element feasible to use for the evaluation of papers? Is it connected with some specific characteristics of research? It may be possible to define “quality” as the togetherness of different aspects of a single paper, such as its capacity of diffusion, the citations it receives in other papers and from scholars other than its author, the rank of the journal where it is published. Of course, this is a topic that academia handles in several ways and through different stages of its governance. The discussion of what means for a paper to be qualitatively good is highly debated in the field, with many points of view and different perspectives conflicting among themselves.

It is impossible to transcend such conflict, but it is not the aim of this work to decide what does it means for a paper to be qualitatively ‘good’. What this work attempts to do, instead, is to infer about the capability Open Science has to impact scientific production, meaning that it allows papers and journals to be diffused easily and better inside the scientific community. At the same time, the accessibility granted by the FAIR principles –a fundamental component of Open Science as intended here – can support the re-usage of papers and resources among members of the same scientific community.

What we intend to do is of course limited by the instruments and data we can have access to. Thanks to SCOPUS, we can retrieve two pieces of information concerning published papers: whether they are available in open access or not; and the number of citations they received. We will have then two main hypotheses to verify: that papers from each university, after the same university has launched an OA policy, will see an increase in mentions (H1); and that it should be possible to observe more papers published into OA by those universities which have implemented OA policies and/or guidelines compared to those that have not done so (H2).

We downloaded from SCOPUS an extract of publications, limited to the field of Social Sciences, from 2000 to 2023. The data retrieved concerned the language used in writing the paper, the author's affiliations – to scoop out all those papers from universities we did not consider in our analysis – and the mentions received at the time of the download. We were also able to ascertain whether the paper was available in Open Access or not. Due to constraints in both time and resources, the analysis has been limited to a specific scientific field, and it is thus prone to bias.

Some words concerning this choice. First of all, no dataset is currently available for use as a starting point for the kind of analysis it has been decided to carry out here. Those data available in the IRIS repository, for example, are not accessible and are directly linked with the VQR of ANVUR (the quality evaluation process of research carried inside Italian Universities). This means that it is possible to access the synthetic final information in the open report published by the organization, but it is not possible to explore the detailed data concerning each university. Moreover, what we are interested in is the granular data pertaining to each paper published by each institution, in order to evaluate our two hypotheses.

As already mentioned, the required data has been extracted from SCOPUS, with a focus on the scientific field of Sociology. Since SCOPUS needs at least some keywords to process requests, we selected all the papers which showed the keyword “Sociology” and which were related to the field of “Social Sciences” and coming from the country “Italy”. This way, almost 9800 papers were identified, published from 2000 to 2023. After collection, the first step involved data polishing for our analysis. We eliminated from the dataset all those papers whose first author was not affiliated to an Italian University. This choice, while apparently limiting our analysis, was nevertheless effective in

helping avoid many false positive results – i.e. papers that first appeared to be linked to the Italian academic community, but that in reality sported only one author affiliated to Italian universities or institutions among ten or more authors.

The second issue with our list of papers and contributions concerned the name format for each university. SCOPUS does not adjust the name to a standard, instead leaving to each contribution the freedom to self-select its affiliation. Thus, a serious issue was met in selecting the universities which at least appeared as signatories to the Messina Declaration, and which had a precise policy on Open Access implemented into their own academic infrastructure. In order to address this issue the Jaccard Similarity has been used to compare the universities already known to have adopted an OA policy with the list of affiliations presented by each paper. Using a chosen value of 0.65 as trade-off, all the papers which resulted with a similarity of 0.65 or superior, were selected as belonging to one of the universities implementing an OA policy. In this case, the chosen university was the one with the best result of similarity. This is of course an approximation, but a necessary one in order to have a model outline. Without any other clear dataset available, this choice established what can be considered a first approach to the use papers as analysis' units.

A total of 56 universities, for 749 observations, based on almost 8000 papers, was obtained this way. The methodology we chose to apply is the so-called “staggered difference-in-difference”, as showed in a study by Callaway & Sant'Anna (2021). This paved the way for the use of the diff-in-diff method as applied not to a single time-period in policy implementation, but to multiple ones instead. Earlier studies concerning the same method (Cfr. Heckman & Al., 1997; Heckman & Al., 1998; Abadie, 2005; de Chaisemartin & D'Haultfœuille, 2018; Callaway & Al., 2018) focused on the application of a single treatment period. In our case, we have instead a number of treatments, linked to when each university enacted its OA policies.

To treat multiple time period at the same moment, we had to use a staggered difference-in-difference, able to capture the differences showing up at different times. For more information on this metho, see Callaway and Sant'Anna (2021).

Table 1 Results of the staggered diff-in-diff, citations as outcome variable

ATT	Std. Error	[95% Confidence Interval]	
-44.7222	32.5435	-108.5063	19.0619

Event time	Estimate	Std. Error	[95% Confidence Interval	
-19	1.293.333	308.052	467.082	2.119.585
-18	-783.333	398.449	-1.852.048	285.381
-17	548.111	269.263	-174.100	1.270.323
-16	-1.241.667	192.326	-1.757.521	-725.812
-15	101.000	289.948	-676.693	878.693
-14	998.554	438.316	-177.090	2.174.198
-13	-371.298	703.256	-2.257.559	1.514.962
-12	-1.153.995	608.638	-2.786.474	478.484
-11	503.908	267.630	-213.924	1.221.740
-10	-41.799	274.644	-778.446	694.847
-9	26.873	252.155	-649.454	703.200
-8	-281.816	360.405	-1.248.487	684.856
-7	566.238	524.200	-839.763	1.972.240
-6	-138.252	382.345	-1.163.771	887.267
-5	-694.702	423.352	-1.830.209	440.805
-4	-220.037	276.883	-962.689	522.615
-3	341.169	233.427	-284.924	967.262
-2	472.232	249.964	-198.219	1.142.682
-1	-33.285	224.606	-635.719	569.149
0	-238.426	280.287	-990.207	513.355
1	-124.202	270.047	-848.518	600.114
2	-225.172	254.085	-906.674	456.329
3	-233.372	319.540	-1.090.438	623.694
4	-280.167	362.912	-1.253.563	693.229

Source: Our analysis, R Script

Figure 2: Staggered diff-in-diff, citations as outcome variable

Source: Our analysis, R Script

To overcome the lack of all the time-period and the scarcity of information, we had to use – as it is visible from the R-Script – an unbalanced panel. We can notice that, at least, the parallel trend assumption seems to be respected. The trend, before the aggregated time-period, seems to do not show a difference between the treated and the non-treated units. After the treatment, we can instead observe a certain tendency, a negative effect of the policy over time. We can also notice a rising standard error which, de facto, tends to describe our model as very imprecise.

We can assume, considered the error, that apparently our first hypothesis is the exact opposite of what we expected. After the launch of the first policies on OA, the number of citations the papers received tended to diminish after the policies are launched.

But, we also have to observe if the number of OA papers published after the policies are launched by each university.

Table 2: Results of the staggered diff-in-diff. OA papers published as outcome variable

ATT	Std. Error	[95% Confidence Interval]	
0.6081	0.2942	0.0316	1.1846 *

Event time	Estimate	Std. Error	[95% Confidence Interval]	
-19	0.0000	NA	NA	NA
-18	0.5000	0.1853	-0.0102	10.102
-17	-0.1778	0.1669	-0.6373	0.2818
-16	-0.1667	0.1956	-0.7052	0.3719
-15	0.0000	NA	NA	NA
-14	-0.0593	0.0431	-0.1780	0.0594
-13	0.2256	0.1291	-0.1299	0.5810
-12	0.0767	0.1136	-0.2361	0.3894
-11	-0.2084	0.1733	-0.6854	0.2686
-10	-0.0424	0.1216	-0.3771	0.2923
-9	0.0132	0.1159	-0.3060	0.3323
-8	-0.0751	0.2097	-0.6523	0.5020
-7	0.0354	0.1251	-0.3091	0.3799
-6	0.2678	0.2212	-0.3412	0.8767
-5	-0.1068	0.1880	-0.6244	0.4107
-4	0.1376	0.1337	-0.2304	0.5057
-3	-0.1095	0.2457	-0.7858	0.5668
-2	-0.2338	0.3344	-11.543	0.6868
-1	0.3218	0.2348	-0.3246	0.9681
0	-0.0537	0.2750	-0.8108	0.7034
1	0.2527	0.3357	-0.6715	11.770
2	-0.0424	0.2527	-0.7382	0.6534
3	0.4593	0.3274	-0.4421	13.607
4	0.6999	0.2938	-0.1090	15.087
5	0.6613	0.4557	-0.5933	19.159
6	0.3591	0.4043	-0.7539	14.720
7	0.7084	0.7429	-13.369	27.537
8	20.890	13.748	-16.958	58.738
9	17.500	14.950	-23.657	58.657
10	-0.1944	0.3192	-10.731	0.6843
-19	0.0000	NA	NA	NA

Source: Our analysis, R Script

Figure 3: Staggered diff-in-diff, OA papers as outcome variable

Source: Our analysis, R Script

In this case, the quality of the data is still not sufficient for being certain about the results. The number of Open Access papers was very low, and it is unclear if it is due to the lack of information on the SCOPUS database or a generally low number of Open Access publications posted on this site altogether. In this case, it is clearer that despite a certain error in the more recent years, tendentially we can observe the number of publications in Open Access to increase after the launch of the policy. Again, it also seems that the assumption of parallel trends works again.

Conclusion

We started this paper stating what does it mean Open Science in the current environment of research academia. We know what how the Berlin and the Messina Declarations tried to underline a new access to Open Science and its derivatives in our context and how different RIs helped shaping the trends of how it is possible to work on and with Open Science – as in the case of the FOSTER Plus and GoFAIR projects.

We observed how the Italian universities, under the umbrella of the Messina Declaration, started to face the possibility to offer better services for publishing in Open Access and in a more open environment of research. We tried to observe the effect of these staggered policies from two different points of view: the number of publications in OA and the number of citations all their papers received.

We decided to rely on the model of Callaway & Sant'Aanna (2021) for a staggered difference-in-difference. Due to the lack of resources at our disposal and of a proper dataset, we focused on the papers in SCOPUS published in the field of Social Sciences with keyword as Sociology. We had to manually control the Open Access one and prepare our own dataset to observe the two effects intended.

We observed that, when we applied our model to the citations, we found a massive standard error even in the aggregated data. Apparently, after the launch of the policies, the number of citations tend to diminish. At the contrary, it seems the number of Open Access papers after the launch of the policies tend to rise.

Our work present some issues. Being a frontier study, these issues can be considered promises for future approaches to the field. The first issue is connected to the lack of data. Italian universities rely on IRIS as system to collect data on their production, but it is difficult – if not impossible – to access the information in the system. We have to rely on external services – SCOPUS, Web of Science, for example – and scoop the data from them. We saw that this can become problematic. The data are never clear, and of course they can be incomplete and not sufficient for the model itself to work precisely. It will be interesting to amplify the sources from which collect the papers and their information – citations and if they are in Open Access – expanding the field of research – from sociology to all the social sciences or also in the STEM field altogether. Another interesting source could be repository dedicated only to Open Access material – as OpenAlex.

In the future, another issue to be solved is to more efficiently connect each university with the publications. We had to rely on a text-conversion to find which papers belonged to which university. This is prone to errors, many errors. Despite trying to correct the issue using the similarity index, that is not sufficient.

Moreover, it will be interesting to observe if the participation in processes and infrastructures – i.e., OPERAS – could become a discriminant of a better diffusion of OS practices in the university context. The diffusion of better policies, as much as new frontier programs in the Social Sciences, and not only, devoted to improve the quality of research, seems to indicate a certain tendency toward this model.

Despite this paper could not be a perfect proof of such movement and only partially address the discussion in the Italian – and European – academia around the role of Open Science and Open Access, the number of projects, papers, and events around this topic indicate that there is a trend which could be interesting to observe in the next years.

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